

An *in silico* simulation of flow mediated dilation reveals that blood pressure and other factors may influence the response independent of endothelial function

Supporting Information

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Supplemental methods

Figure S1. *In vivo* data acquisition. (a) Diameter tracking and flow velocity in the brachial artery acquired by ultrasound, as displayed by the Brachial Analyzer software. (b) Spectral Doppler ultrasound flow velocity waveform for a single cardiac cycle. (c) Post-processed flow velocity waveform assuming a parabolic velocity profile.

Table S1. *In vivo* FMD test results. Baseline, D_b , and peak, D_p , vessel diameters measured in 8 subjects and calculated FMD test values using $(D_p - D_b)/D_b \times 100\%$.

Subject No.	Baseline Diameter [mm]	Peak Diameter [mm]	FMD [%]
1	4.4	4.5	3.2
2	3.0	3.3	8.7
3	3.3	3.6	7.6
4	4.0	4.4	10.6
5	2.3	2.5	6.5
6	2.4	2.5	7.2
7	3.9	4.2	8.3
8	3.4	3.6	5.3
Mean $\pm$ SD	3.3 $\pm$ 0.7	3.6 $\pm$ 0.7	7.2 $\pm$ 2.1

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Table S2. Arterial parameters immediately before cuff inflation. $R_{in} \rightarrow R_{out}$: diastolic cross-sectional radii at the inlet and outlet of the arterial segment. $c_{in} \rightarrow c_{out}$: diastolic wave speed at the inlet and outlet of the arterial segment. Peripheral resistances correspond to the sum of the resistances R_1 and R_2 in Figure 1b (main document).

Arterial segment	Length (cm)	$R_{in} \rightarrow R_{out}$ (mm)	$c_{in} \rightarrow c_{out}$ (m/s)	Arterial compliance ($10^{-10} \text{ m}^3 \text{ Pa}^{-1}$)	Peripheral resistance ($10^{10} \text{ Pa s m}^{-3}$)	Peripheral compliance ($10^{-10} \text{ m}^3 \text{ Pa}^{-1}$)
1. Ascending Aorta	6	14.9 $\rightarrow$ 14.7	4.6 $\rightarrow$ 4.6	18.334	-	-
2. Aortic Arch I	2	12.9 $\rightarrow$ 12.9	4.6 $\rightarrow$ 4.6	4.654	-	-
3. Brachiocephalic	3.4	6.99 $\rightarrow$ 6.99	4.64 $\rightarrow$ 4.64	2.285	-	-
4. Right Subclavian I	3.4	6 $\rightarrow$ 5.5	4.7 $\rightarrow$ 4.75	1.497	-	-
5. Right Carotid	9.4	4 $\rightarrow$ 3.45	5.13 $\rightarrow$ 5.45	1.395	-	-
6. Right Vertebral	14.9	1.85 $\rightarrow$ 1.4	7.54 $\rightarrow$ 8.64	0.183	-	-
7. Right Brachial	42.2	5.5 $\rightarrow$ 2.36	4.75 $\rightarrow$ 6.61	7.892	-	-
8. Right Radial	23.5	1.3 $\rightarrow$ 1.2	8.93 $\rightarrow$ 9.23	0.132	-	-
9. Right Ulnar I	6.7	2.15 $\rightarrow$ 2.15	6.96 $\rightarrow$ 6.96	0.189	-	-
10. Right Interosseous	7.9	0.91 $\rightarrow$ 0.91	10.2 $\rightarrow$ 10.2	0.02	1.243	0.4308
11. Right Ulnar II	17.1	2 $\rightarrow$ 1.83	7.24 $\rightarrow$ 7.59	0.340	-	-
12. Right Internal Carotid	17.8	2.85 $\rightarrow$ 2.15	5.98 $\rightarrow$ 6.96	0.819	-	-
13. Right External Carotid	4.1	2.5 $\rightarrow$ 2.25	6.41 $\rightarrow$ 6.79	0.158	-	-
14. Aortic Arch II	3.9	12.4 $\rightarrow$ 12.4	4.6 $\rightarrow$ 4.6	8.384	-	-
15. Left Carotid	13.9	3.7 $\rightarrow$ 3.22	5.29 $\rightarrow$ 5.62	1.677	-	-
16. Left Internal Carotid	17.8	2.65 $\rightarrow$ 2.05	6.21 $\rightarrow$ 7.14	0.674	-	-
17. Left External Carotid	4.1	2.35 $\rightarrow$ 2.15	6.63 $\rightarrow$ 6.96	0.134	-	-
18. Descending Thoracic Aorta I	5.2	11 $\rightarrow$ 9.99	4.6 $\rightarrow$ 4.61	8.009	-	-
19. Left Subclavian	3.4	5.5 $\rightarrow$ 5	4.75 $\rightarrow$ 4.83	1.215	-	-
20. Left Vertebral	14.8	1.85 $\rightarrow$ 1.4	7.54 $\rightarrow$ 8.64	0.182	-	-
21. Left Brachial	42.2	4.65 $\rightarrow$ 2.36	4.91 $\rightarrow$ 6.61	5.645	-	-
22. Left Radial	23.5	1.3 $\rightarrow$ 1.2	8.93 $\rightarrow$ 9.23	0.132	-	-
23. Left Ulnar I	6.7	2.15 $\rightarrow$ 2.15	6.96 $\rightarrow$ 6.96	0.189	-	-
24. Left Interosseous	7.9	0.91 $\rightarrow$ 0.91	10.2 $\rightarrow$ 10.2	0.02	1.243	0.4308

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25. Left Ulnar II	17.1	2 → 1.83	7.24 → 7.59	0.340	-	-
26. Intercostal arteries	8	1.2 → 1.2	9.23 → 9.23	0.04	0.2649	3.811
27. Descending Thoracic Aorta II	10.4	8.7 → 7.1	4.61 → 4.64	9.039	-	-
28. Abdominal Aorta I	5.3	6.1 → 6.1	4.69 → 4.69	2.660	-	-
29. Celiac I	2	3.8 → 3.8	5.23 → 5.23	0.313	-	-
30. Celiac II	1	3 → 3	5.82 → 5.82	0.079	-	-
31. Gastric	7.1	2.9 → 2.75	5.92 → 6.09	0.47	0.5495	0.7627
32. Hepatic	6.6	2.4 → 2.4	6.55 → 6.55	0.26	0.2363	1.955
33. Splenic	6.3	2 → 2	7.24 → 7.24	0.14	0.3174	1.482
34. Superior Mesenteric	5.9	3 → 3	5.82 → 5.82	0.46	0.1465	3.096
35. Abdominal Aorta II	1	5.9 → 5.9	4.7 → 4.7	0.466	-	-
36. Left renal	3.2	2.6 → 2.6	6.27 → 6.27	0.16	0.1049	4.93
37. Abdominal Aorta III	1	5.7 → 5.7	4.72 → 4.72	0.432	-	-
38. Right renal	3.2	2.6 → 2.6	6.27 → 6.27	0.16	0.1049	4.93
39. Abdominal Aorta IV	10.6	5.5 → 5.3	4.75 → 4.77	4.044	-	-
40. Inferior Mesenteric	5	1.6 → 1.6	8.12 → 8.12	0.06	0.5373	0.8806
41. Abdominal Aorta V	1	5.2 → 5	4.79 → 4.83	0.334	-	-
42. Left Common Iliac	5.8	3.68 → 3.5	5.3 → 5.41	0.774	-	-
43. Right Common Iliac	5.9	3.68 → 3.5	5.3 → 5.41	0.787	-	-
44. Left External Iliac	14.4	2.8 → 2.7	6.03 → 6.15	0.871	-	-
45. Left Internal Iliac	5	2.63 → 2.63	6.23 → 6.23	0.26	0.5337	0.7897
46. Left Femoral	44.3	2.5 → 1.9	6.41 → 7.44	1.372	-	-
47. Left Deep Femoral	12.6	1.5 → 1.25	8.37 → 9.09	0.09	0.461	1.278
48. Left Posterior Tibial	32.1	1.55 → 1.4	8.24 → 8.64	0.29	0.3524	1.662
49. Left Anterior Tibial	34.3	1.3 → 1.15	8.93 → 9.39	0.18	0.5362	1.121
50. Right External Iliac	14.5	2.8 → 2.7	6.03 → 6.15	0.877	-	-
51. Right Internal Iliac	5	2.63 → 2.63	6.23 → 6.23	0.26	0.5337	0.7897
52. Right Femoral	44.4	2.5 → 1.9	6.41 → 7.44	1.376	-	-
53. Right Deep Femoral	12.7	1.5 → 1.25	8.37 → 9.09	0.09	0.461	1.278
54. Right Posterior Tibial	32.2	1.55 → 1.4	8.24 → 8.64	0.29	0.3517	1.666

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55. Right Anterior Tibial	34.4	1.3 → 1.15	8.93 → 9.39	0.18	0.5353	1.124
56. Basilar II	1.5	2 → 1.9	7.24 → 7.44	0.031	-	-
57. Basilar I	1	1.9 → 1.35	7.44 → 8.79	0.012	-	-
58. Right Posterior Cerebral I	0.4	0.95 → 0.95	10.1 → 10.1	0.001	-	-
59. Left Posterior Cerebral I	0.4	0.95 → 0.95	10.1 → 10.1	0.001	-	-
60. Right Posterior Communicating	0.4	0.75 → 0.75	10.8 → 10.8	0.001	-	-
61. Left Posterior Communicating	0.4	0.75 → 0.75	10.8 → 10.8	0.001	-	-
62. Right Posterior Cerebral II	5.9	1 → 0.9	9.89 → 10.3	0.02	0.9738	0.1669
63. Left Posterior Cerebral II	5.9	1 → 0.9	9.89 → 10.3	0.02	0.9738	0.1669
64. Right Distal Internal Carotid I	0.4	1.95 → 1.9	7.34 → 7.44	0.008	-	-
65. Left Distal Internal Carotid I	0.4	1.95 → 1.9	7.34 → 7.44	0.008	-	-
66. Right Anterior Cerebral I	1.2	1.05 → 1	9.72 → 9.89	0.004	-	-
67. Left Anterior Cerebral I	1.2	1.05 → 1	9.72 → 9.89	0.004	-	-
68. Right Middle Cerebral (M1)	0.8	1.5 → 1.4	8.37 → 8.64	0.007	-	-
69. Right Sup. Middle Cerebral (M2)	7.1	1 → 1	9.89 → 9.89	0.02	0.7799	0.206
70. Right Inf. Middle Cerebral (M2)	7	1 → 1	9.89 → 9.89	0.02	0.7799	0.206
71. Left Middle Cerebral (M1)	0.8	1.5 → 1.4	8.37 → 8.64	0.007	-	-
72. Left Sup. Middle Cerebral (M2)	7.1	1 → 1	9.89 → 9.89	0.02	0.7799	0.206
73. Left Inf. Middle Cerebral (M2)	7	1 → 1	9.89 → 9.89	0.02	0.7799	0.206
74. Right Anterior Cerebral II	2.4	0.9 → 0.85	10.3 → 10.4	0.01	1.098	0.1488
75. Anterior Communicating	0.4	0.65 → 0.65	11.2 → 11.2	0.000	-	-
76. Left Anterior Cerebral II	2.4	0.9 → 0.85	10.3 → 10.4	0.01	1.098	0.1488
77. Right Internal Carotid Sinus	1.1	2.15 → 1.95	6.96 → 7.34	0.027	-	-
78. Right Ophthalmic	1.1	0.5 → 0.25	11.9 → 13.1	0.00	22.06	0.02396
79. Left Internal Carotid Sinus	1.1	2.15 → 1.95	6.96 → 7.34	0.027	-	-
80. Left Ophthalmic	1.1	0.5 → 0.25	11.9 → 13.1	0.00	22.06	0.02396
81. Right External Carotid II	6.1	2 → 1.75	7.24 → 7.76	0.114	-	-
82. Right Superior Thyroid / Ascending Pharyngeal / Lingual / Facial / Occipital	10.1	1.4 → 1.4	8.64 → 8.64	0.08	0.6469	0.7513

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83. Left External Carotid II	6.1	2 → 1.75	7.24 → 7.76	0.114	-	-
84. Left Superior Thyroid / Ascending Pharyngeal / Lingual / Facial / Occipital	10.1	1.1 → 0.8	9.56 → 10.6	0.03	2.058	0.2453
85. Right Superior Temporal	6.1	1.6 → 1.5	8.12 → 8.37	0.064	-	-
86. Right Maxillary Artery	9.1	1.1 → 0.5	9.56 → 11.9	0.02	5.394	0.09583
87. Left Superior Temporal	6.1	1.6 → 1.5	8.12 → 8.37	0.064	-	-
88. Left Maxillary Artery	9.1	1.1 → 0.5	9.56 → 11.9	0.02	5.394	0.09583
89. Right Sup. Temporal Frontal	10	1.1 → 0.7	9.56 → 11	0.02	2.708	0.1878
90. Right Sup. Temporal Parietal	10.1	1.1 → 0.7	9.56 → 11	0.02	2.708	0.1878
91. Left Sup. Temporal Frontal	10	1.1 → 0.7	9.56 → 11	0.02	2.708	0.1878
92. Left Sup. Temporal Parietal	10.1	1.1 → 0.7	9.56 → 11	0.02	2.708	0.1878
93. Right Anterior Choroidal	3.6	0.75 → 0.65	10.8 → 11.2	0.00	1.925	0.08704
94. Right Distal Internal Carotid II	0.4	1.9 → 1.9	7.44 → 7.44	0.008	-	-
95. Left Anterior Choroidal	3.6	0.75 → 0.65	10.8 → 11.2	0.00	1.925	0.08704
96. Left Distal Internal Carotid II	0.4	1.9 → 1.9	7.44 → 7.44	0.008	-	-
97. Right Deep Palmar Arch III	3	0.65 → 0.65	11.2 → 11.2	0.003	-	-
98. Right Superf. Palmar Arch III	1	1.11 → 1.11	9.52 → 9.52	0.004	-	-
99. Right Deep Palmar Arch I	3	1.17 → 1.17	9.33 → 9.33	0.014	-	-
100. Right Superf. Palmar Arch I	1	1.52 → 1.52	8.32 → 8.32	0.010	-	-
101. Right Superf. Palmar Arch II	1	0.69 → 0.69	11.1 → 11.1	0.001	-	-
102. Right Digital Artery III	3	1.05 → 1.05	9.72 → 9.72	0.01	0.9227	0.5735
103. Right Digital Artery II	3	1.08 → 1.08	9.62 → 9.62	0.01	0.87	0.6068
104. Right Digital Artery IV	1.5	0.74 → 0.74	10.9 → 10.9	0.00	1.91	0.2849
105. Right Digital Artery I	2.5	1.03 → 1.03	9.79 → 9.79	0.01	0.9605	0.5519
106. Right Deep Palmar Arch II	3	0.75 → 0.75	10.8 → 10.8	0.004	-	-
107. Left Deep Palmar Arch III	3	0.65 → 0.65	11.2 → 11.2	0.003	-	-
108. Left Superf. Palmar Arch III	1	1.11 → 1.11	9.52 → 9.52	0.004	-	-
109. Left Deep Palmar Arch I	3	1.17 → 1.17	9.33 → 9.33	0.014	-	-
110. Left Superf. Palmar Arch I	1	1.52 → 1.52	8.32 → 8.32	0.010	-	-

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111. Left Superf. Palmar Arch II	1	0.69 → 0.69	11.1 → 11.1	0.001	-	-
112. Left Digital Artery III	3	1.05 → 1.05	9.72 → 9.72	0.01	0.9227	0.5735
113. Left Digital Artery II	3	1.08 → 1.08	9.62 → 9.62	0.01	0.87	0.6068
114. Left Digital Artery IV	1.5	0.74 → 0.74	10.9 → 10.9	0.00	1.91	0.2849
115. Left Digital Artery I	2.5	1.03 → 1.03	9.79 → 9.79	0.01	0.9605	0.5519
116. Left Deep Palmar Arch II	3	0.75 → 0.75	10.8 → 10.8	0.004	-	-

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Supplemental results

Figure S2. *In vivo* and *in silico* waveforms in the brachial artery. *In vivo* flow velocity waveforms for all 8 subjects (top) and *in silico* flow velocity (middle) and pressure (bottom) waveforms at the baseline, inflation, deflation and recovery stages of FMD, for the endothelial response function model with baseline parameters.

Figure S3. *In silico* FMD values as a function of the measurement site along the brachial artery. All model parameters were taken at baseline.